

WOMEN AND GIRLS EDUCATION: COURAGE AND RESILIENCE IN THE FACE OF INJUSTICES IN NIGERIA.

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the influence of Culture, Sexual violence and Religious chaos on courage and Resilience of girl-child education in the face of injustice in Nigeria. To guide the study, three Purposes, three Research questions, and three Null Hypotheses were formulated. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The descriptive survey research design was used for the study. Population of the study comprise of all women in Akwa Ibom North-east senatorial district using accidental sampling technique. The research questionnaire was design for the study and were subjected to the reliability test on 150 respondents and the date collected for the reliability test were subjected to Cronbach alpha reliability test, which yielded a coefficient of 8.06. findings of the study shows that Culture, Sexual violence and Religious chaos significantly influence courage and resilience of girl-child. The study recommended that Government and Media should create more awareness on girl-child education its benefit. The study made known that girl-child education is not only beneficial to the girl but to family, communities and nation at large.

Keyword: Girl-child education, courage, resilience, culture, sexual violence, Religious chaos.

Introduction

Education is an inalienable right of all citizens irrespective of gender, age and nationality, Education is an instrument par excellence which equips an individual with the right skills, knowledge, ability, competence, attitude,

behavior and values in order to function effectively in society. Education is equally a means to an end which assist citizens of a nation to develop their full potentials and capacity to contribute to societal development as well as to attain sustainable live hood. Michael (2011) described education as a key to a successful living, especially girl – child education. Girl-child education is a catch-all-term for a complex set of issues and debates surrounding primary, secondary, tertiary and health education in particular for girls and women.

Omede and Agahiu, (2016) opined that denying the girl child access to education implies making her a dysfunctional member of the society. A girl child by definition is a biological female offspring from birth to eighteen years of age. Globally, about 121 million children are out of school, 65 million are girls with over 80 percent of these girls in sub-Sahara Africa (UNICEF as cited in Omede and Agahiu, 2016).

Successive governments in Nigeria have over the years made concerned efforts in a bid to bridge the gender disparity on education in different ways. These include: the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Right Act of 1948; the Nigerian Child Rights Act of 2003 which states that a female child who becomes pregnant before completing her education shall be given opportunity after delivery to continue with education on the basis of her individual ability; the establishment of Universal Basis Education Act in 2004; the establishment of education for AIC Goals (EFA), sustainable Development goals (SDGs), among others.

In the traditional Nigerian society, there exists the degenerated believed that woman are second class citizens. A woman is considered as a man's property or pleasure object. She is also considered as a “machine” meant for producing children. This situation has resulted in unfair treatment of women especially with regards to education. Education of girls has begun to receive the attention it deserves, for thousands of years men have believed that the proper place for the women is the home and that the home can be properly managed by ignorant women. But today, other views are changing the views of women and several influences are steadily changing the old-fashioned attitudes. Fortunate Nigerian women who enjoy a good education have prove their abilities in several walks of life. They successfully attitude doctors, teachers, lawyers, professors, engineering and a lot more. They are also found in industry, commerce and public administration. These set of women have proved the case for women's education by demonstrating their usefulness outside the home.

UNICEF (2017) noted that investing in girl's education transforms the communities, countries and the entire world. Girls who receive education are less likely to marry young and more likely to live healthy and productive lives. UNICEF further stated that educated girls earn higher income, participate in decision that most affect them, and build better future for themselves and their

families. It is also pertinent to state that girls who go to school and complete schooling are able to have more access to social positions, better pay-jobs and higher income.

Courage has been identified as integral to the professional development of girl child. (Hawkins and Morse, 2014). But is a complex and multifaceted concept used in varying ways and contexts in the education. Courage involves persevering through adversity and resistance to accomplish improvement, even though the individual experiences anxiety, uncertainty, and apprehension in doing so. (Cleary and Horsfall, 2014; Gruber, 2012).

Resilience refers to the capacity to cope with stress and catastrophe, offering individual the ability to bounce back from adversity and successfully adapt to it.

Ledesma, (2019) defined Resilience as a class of phenomena characterized by good outcomes in spite of serious threats to adaptation of development. Notability, the concept of thriving refers to a person's ability to go beyond her original level of functioning and to grow and function despite adversity. (2018) opined that resilience is the capacity of a system to adapt successfully to significant challenges that threaten the function, viability, or development of the system.

Thus, promotion of education among girls across Nigeria and particularly in rural area would go a long way in bridging the wide gap of inequality and help in accelerating the process of social, economic and political changes in the status of women in the society. It is against this background that this study is carried out to determine the influence of culture, sexual violence and Religion Chaos on courage and resilience of girl's child education in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Education is key to creating, applying and spreading knowledge thereby ensuring the development of dynamic, globally competitive economic. Despite the introduction of western education in Nigeria in 1842, which women were encouraged to acquire western education? During the time of missionaries, a lot of effort was made in promoting women education in Nigeria. This brought about the establishment of girls schools.

Although, education of girls has begun to receive the attention, it is observed that some part of Nigeria is lacking behind. In Yoruba land some people still believe, despite the socialization level that when you train females, they end up being other person's properties so they feel it is not necessary wasting one's money.

Again, despite girl-child education gaining ground in the country, the question still remains how many of these women occupy key positions in their

various callings. In recent time, educated women as a pressure group have risen to imbalances in sex participation in rates in education, civil service and invariably national development in significant percentage of the nation's population. In view of the above, the researcher sought to determine how culture, sexual violence and religious chaos would influence courage and resilience of girl-child education in Nigeria.

1.3 Purpose of the study

This study sought to:

1. Determine the extent of influence of cultural influence on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.
2. Determine the extent of influence of sexual violence on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria
3. Determine the extent of influence of religious chaos on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.

1.4 Significance of the study

The importance of education in the life of an individual particularly, the girl-child cannot be overemphasized. Therefore this study would be useful to girl-child, women, parents, communities, nations and government at large.

Kiki (2010) asserted that the girl-child needs to be educated to acquire knowledge and skills needed to advance her status for social interventions and self-improvement. Educating the girl-child produces mothers who are educated and will in turn educate their children. When girl-child is educated, she realizes her full potential and enables her to take decision that affects her life no matter the level of injustice on them. Educated women contribute to families, communities, societies and nations at large.

1.5 Research Question

The following research question guided the study;

1. How does culture influence courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.
2. How does sexual violence influence courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.
3. How does religious chaos influence courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.

Hypotheses of the study

1. Culture does not have significant influence on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.
2. Sexual violence does not have significant influence on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.
3. Religious chaos does not have significant influence on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

Richardson's Meta-theory of Resilience and Resiliency (2002)

Richardson's (2002) conceptualized that resilience is a force within everyone that drives them to seek bely-actualization, altruism, wisdom and be in harmony with a spiritual source of strength. He identified three different waves of resiliency enquiring characteristic of people who effectively cope with and grow through disruption. The process in which such people acquire these characteristics and the recognition of innate resilience and the capacity to grow and develop, resilient reintegration develops by the strengthening of the resilient qualities.

According to the theory an individual begins at a state of physical, mental and spiritual homeostasis (biopsychospiritual) homeostasis-figure 1), then disruption occurs, in this case the five tragedy. After the disruption the individuals reintegrated to homeostasis in one of the four ways; resilient reintegration, re-integration back to homeostasis, re-integration with loss and dysfunctional re-integration.

The three wave's theory proposed by Richardson (2002) on resiliency explains the component of the resilience theory postulated by Richards et al (1990). The first wave describes to rebound from qualities one must possess to rebound from adversity. The second wave describe the resiliency process of coping with challenges and coming out of it with improved protective factors. It also accounts for reintegration, which is a person's ability to back into either the same situational mindset, or an improved one, after a loss. The third waves is innate resilience which serves to identify an individual's motives and experiences that cause the utilization of resilience as a force that drives a girl-

child to effectively cope with and grow through disruption cultural influence, sexual violence, Religious chaos and injustices face by them in girl-child education in Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

The girl-child is a female homo sapiens of unmarried age that is defined by the anatomical and physiological characteristics that set her apart from her male counterpart. Girl-child education incorporates the necessary altitude, cultural and behavioural training which parents give to their daughter at home to enable them become useful, resourceful and respectful citizens of their societies.

Okernmor et al, (2012) girl-child education is a catch-all term for a complexity of issues and debates surrounding education (primary education, secondary education, tertiary education and health education for females).

Culture is a fundamental aspect of human society and profoundly impacts our daily lives. It encompasses a wide range of beliefs, values and norms shared by a group and passed down from generation to generation. Culture plays an important role in shaping how we communicate with others. It determines how we interact with others and the norms governing our human behavior. Our professional choices. It influences our ideas about success, happiness, and the meaning of life and can affect our ever-evolving and dynamic aspect of our lives that countries to shape us in new and meaningful way.

Culture is a complex whole which includes knowledge, beliefs, arts, normal, customs and any other capabilities acquired by man as a member of the society. It is the sum total of a given society's way of life moulded and shaped by prevailing circumstances and environment (Nakpodia, 2010).

According to World Health Organization 2002 (WHO) Sexual violence is any sexual act, attempt to obtain a sexual act, unwanted sexual comments or advance, or acts to traffic or otherwise directed against a person's sexuality using coercion, by any person regardless of their relationship to the victim, in any setting, including but not limited to home and work. In addition, sexual

violence also take place when someone is not able to give consent for instance, while intoxicated, drugged, asleep or mentally incapacitated. Sexual violence, including sexual harassment, frequently occurs in institutions assumed to be “safe”, such as schools where perpetrators include peers and teachers.

Nigeria is a country where Christianity and Islam enjoy large fellowship. As such the country has been divided into two religious camps. It is often claimed that Nigeria has over 200 million people and about half are Muslims while the remaining percentage are either Christians or Traditionalists. Thus, it is interesting to note that these two religious bodies (Christianity and Islam) are always competing with each other for religious space. Unfortunately, the political class did not hesitate to wrongly use them gain both political and economic advantages over their opponents. Therefore, religious chaos becomes inevitable. Wrong use of religion has resulted to wanton destruction of lives and property. During religious conflicts, many people have been killed, maimed and wounded. In fact, religious chaos create an atmosphere of national insecurity and uncertainty which are inimical to economic growth and development.

Courage has been identified as integral to the professional development of girl child. Alpers, et al (2012); Hawkins and Morse, 2014). It is a complex and multifaceted concept used in varying ways and contexts in the girl-child education literature. To cultivate courage, a girl-child must look at challenges as opportunities and should not stop until she has found solutions to them.

Resilience refers to the capacity to cope with stress and catastrophe, offering the girl-child the ability to bounce back from adversity and successfully adapt to it (Nairayanan, 2008). Resilience is also defined as a class of phenomena characterized by good outcomes in spite of serious threats to adaptation of development.

Notably, the concept of thriving refers to a person's ability to go beyond her original level of functioning and to grow and function despite repeated exposure to stressful experience Ledesma, 2014.

Girls/Women of High Esteem in Akwalbom State

1. ImaobongNseUko – World's Fastest U18 Female Quarter 2021
2. Hilda Bassey (Hilda Bassey (Hilda Baci) Guinness World Record breaker in Cong hours cooking 2023.
3. Mrs. Ememobong. ICSAA Chairperson in Akwalbom State.
4. Prof. Eno B. Usoro. DVC Admin, University of Uyo – Akwalbom State
5. Prof. Comfort Ekpo – Former VC – Unversity of Uyo – AkwalbomState.
6. Dr. UyaiAkpanobong – Director Centre for Gender studies – University of Uyo.
7. Justice IdongesitNtem – Former Chief judge of Akwalbom State
8. Justice EkaetteObot. Chief Judge of Akwalbom State.
9. Dr. Akon Eyakenyi – Deputy Governor – Akwalbom State.
10. Engr. Ekemini Eddy Umoh. Girl Child Education Advocate and Engineer.

Empirical Framework Work

According to Mercy (2017) in her work “an assessment on factors militating against girl child education” The researcher investigated the factors that militate against girl child education which she listed as poor family background, religious isolation, disability, early marriage and pregnancy, sexual violence, cultural discrimination and attitudes against women's states and roles. The work has it focus and on Enugu State Nigeria. However, the researcher engaged secondary sources in gathering information. The author maintained to power, prestige, approval, survival, greatness and advancement for men and female. The researcher identified some of the actions that could be taken to address the challenges which are fostering a gender inclusive culture at family level through education, enforcement of legislation on principles of gender equality in education and banning street hawking early child marriage and forced labor.

Maji and Maji (2016), in their presentation “Encouraging girl-child education for better reproductive health in Nigeria. The study aimed to re-emphasize and reawakened the mind of humanity on the undisputable

importance of girl-child education as a tool for improving reproductive health in Nigeria. The researcher made use of secondary sources in gathering data. The authors maintained that the importance of girl-child education can be over emphasized in national health system, because it reduces infant and child mortality rates, women's fertility rate, maternal mortality rates, early child marriage, improved communication between couple and sense of control over other related infections. The researchers concluded with the word "Education is indeed important for girl-child especially now that the nation is striving to achieve higher level of healthcare delivery".

Adam, (2016), also made his own contribution in his article titled "Correlate of poverty and culture on girl-child out of schools in Bauchi State, Nigeria". The purpose of the study was to find out the correlation with girl-child out of school in Bauchi. The researcher got more information to facilitate his work from secondary source. correlation research design, population and sample size, questionnaires and interview from the analysis, the researcher was able to deduce that there is a relationship between poverty and girl-child out of school, also that there is a relationship between culture and girl-child out of school. The author concluded by saying that government should introduce and maintain a school feeding program, subsidize school uniform for the poor and should use sanction to ensure that culture does not hinder girl-child education.

Methodology

Area of the Study

This study was carried out in Uyo Senatorial District of Akwalbom State. The area Comcast the entire geography area of nine (9) Local Government Area; Uyo, Ibesikpo, Uruan, NsitAtai, Itu, NsitUbium, Etinan, NsitIbom and IbionoIbom. The Uyo senatorial district otherwise known as Akwalbom North-East has its Headquarters in Uyo. As of 2019, the district has 94 Registration Areas (RAs) and 987 Polling Unit (PUs) and its collation centre is located in Uyo Local Government.

The 2013 approximated Area (km²) of Akwalbom North East are as follows:

L.G.A.	2013 Approximate Area (km ²)
Uyo	- 156.000
Uruan	- 422.000
Ibesikpo	- 192.000
Itu	- 273.000
Ibiono	- 333.000

NsitAtai	-	135.000
NsitIbom	-	109.000
NsitUbium	-	243.000
Etinan	-	164.000
Total Approximated Area	-	1,918,000km²

Population of the Study

The population of the study consist of all women in nine Local Government Areas that make up Akwa Ibom North-east senatorial district. According to 2015 projected census data:

L.G.A.	Projected Population 2015
Uyo	- 196,343
Uruan	- 75,676
Ibesikpo	- 88,129
Itu	- 81,596
Ibiono	- 120,865
NsitAtai	- 47,313
NsitIbom	- 69,120
NsitUbium	- 81,548
Etinan	- 108,668

This data is gotten from the projected census estimate of 2015 in Akwa Ibom State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size of this study consist of 200 women in Akwa Ibom North-east district. Accidental random sampling was used for the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

The researcher developed a 15Item Structure Girl-Child Education courage and resilience Questionnaire (GCECR) which was used for data collection. The instrument was designed to seek information from respondents on how culture,

sexual violence and religious chaos influences courage and Resilience of girl-child education in the face of injustice in Nigeria.

Validation of the Instrument

The researcher instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts in Business education department, university of Uyo. The content, suitability, language and arrangement of the items were accessed. The expert's comments and input were incorporated and used for modification of the final copy of the instrument.

Reliability of the instrument

The instruments were administered to 150 female students of University of Uyo who does not form part of the respondents. Cronbach alpha was utilized to establish the reliability co-efficient of the instrument which stood at 0.86 on the basis of high reliability index.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher visited schools, some Government ministries, banks, major market and church. The researcher with the help of research assistant administered the questionnaire to women. Completed copies collected instantly to avoid any lost.

Method of Data Analysis

Research question were answered using mean and standard deviation while population t-test (t) was used in testing the hypotheses formulated for the study at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Questions

How does culture influence courage and resilience of girl child in Nigeria.

Table I: Mean analysis of the influence of culture on courage and resilience of girl child in the face of injustice in Nigeria.

Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Culture	200	17.31	2.66
Reference Mean Score	00	12.5	0.00

The result in Table 1 shows the observed mean of 17.31 and the reference mean score of 12.5 comparatively, the observed mean is greater than the reference mean. Therefore, there is an influence of culture on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.

Research Question 2

How does sexual violence influence courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.

Table 2: Mean analysis of the influence of sexual violence on courage and resilience of girl child in the face of injustice in Nigeria.

Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Sexual violence	200	17.19	2.84
Reference Mean Score	00	12.5	0.00

The result in Table 1 shows the observed mean of 17.19 and the reference mean score of 12.5 comparatively, the observed mean is greater than the reference mean. Therefore, there is an influence of sexual violence on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.

Research Questions 3

How does religious chaos influence courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.

Table 3: Mean analysis of the influence of religious chaos on courage and resilience of girl child in the face of injustice in Nigeria.

Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Religious chaos	200	17.29	2.74
Reference Mean Score	00	12.5	0.00

The result in Table 1 shows the observed mean of 17.29 and the reference mean score of 12.5 comparatively, the observed mean is greater than the reference mean. Therefore, there is an influence of religious chaos on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis I

There is no significance influence of culture on courage and resilience of girl-child in Nigeria.

Table 4: One sample t-test of the influence of culture on courage and resilience of girl child in Nigeria.

Test Value = 12.5						
Variable	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t-value	Sig.
Culture	200	17.31	2.66	199	25.53	.000

The entries in table 4 shows that calculated t-value of 25.53 is greater than the probability value of ($p < 0.05$) 0.00 with degree of freedom of 199. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims that culture does not have significant influence on courage and resilience of girl child is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant influence of culture on courage and resilience of girl child in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significance influence of sexual violence on courage and resilience of girl child in Nigeria.

Table 5: One sample t-test of the influence of Sexual violence on courage and resilience of girl child in Nigeria.

Test Value = 12.5						
Variable	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t-value	Sig.
Sexual violence	200	17.19	2.84	199	23.31	.000

The entries in table 5 shows that calculated t-value of 23.31 is greater than the probability value of ($p < 0.05$) 0.00 with degree of freedom of 199. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims that sexual violence does not have significant influence on courage and resilience of girl child is rejected. Therefore, there is a

significant influence of sexual violence on courage and resilience of girl child in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significance influence of religious chaos on courage and resilience of girl child in Nigeria.

Table 6: One sample t-test of the influence of culture on courage and resilience of girl child in Nigeria.

Test Value = 12.5						
Variable	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t-value	Sig.
Religious Chaos	200	17.19	2.84	199	24.17	.000

The entries in table 6 shows that calculated t-value of 24.17 is greater than the probability value of ($p < 0.05$) 0.00 with degree of freedom of 199. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims that religious chaos does not have significant influence on courage and resilience of girl child is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant influence of religious chaos on courage and resilience of girl child in Nigeria.

Discussion of the Findings

Finding of the research hypothesis one, revealed a significant influence of culture on courage and resilience of girl child in Akwa Ibom North-east Senatorial district. The present finding is in line with Adam, (2016). The researcher found that there is a relationship between culture and girl-child out of school. The author concluded by saying that government should introduce sanction to ensure that culture does not hinder girl-child education.

Finding of the research hypothesis two, revealed a significant influence of sexual violence on courage and resilience of girl-child in Akwa Ibom North-east Senatorial district. The finding is in line with the study conducted by Mercy (2017). The author list sexual violence as one of the factor militating against girl-child education in Nigeria. The researcher identified some of the action that could be taken to address the challenges such as banning street hawking, early child marriage and forced labour.

Finding of the research hypothesis three, revealed a significant influence of religious chaos on courage and resilience of girl-child in Akwa Ibom North-east Senatorial district. This findings is in line with the study

conducted on factors militating against girl-child education by Mercy (2017). The researcher identifies Religious isolation as one of the factor militating against girl-child education.

Conclusion:

Based on the finding of the study, it is concluded that, Culture, Sexual violence and Religious chaos has a significance influence on courage and Resilience of girl child education in Akwa Ibom North-east senatorial district.

Recommendation:

The following recommendation were made from the finding:

1. Nigerian government and media should increase public awareness and implement rules that forbid discrimination against girl-child education in order to raise the standard of female education.
2. Government should establish a special court to try gender-based violence offenders.
3. Government should provide platforms for women and girls voices to be heard.

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